

CONSUMER ADOPTION BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS MOBILE APPS

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Abstract

The way consumers are interacting with the brands are been revolutionized through Mobile Apps (MA). Customer experiences on empirical research are less, hence this research aims to analyze how MA integration in shopping can lead to improved customer experience. An online survey was conducted to the consumers of Mobile Apps (MA). Total responses were analyzed using Partial Least squares-structural equation modelling. In addition, the study has practical implications for retailers deploying Mobile Apps (MA) in services offered to their customers.

Introduction

In order to increase confidence, trust and engage with consumers, m-commerce is seen as the new medium. Internet access in towns and villages has been facilitated through Internet and broadband adoption. Internet access has been accelerated during the COVID-19 years which led to the Technology adoption across the globe. In the year 2000 access to the Internet was available with 6% of the world population had and today more than 70% of the world's population has Internet access. In the last two decades, Internet availability and adoption have rapidly grown as Internet and connectivity have become the core energy and core environment for all activities. However the acceleration brought by the pandemic changed the pace all together.

The way businesses interact with the consumers can be revolutionized through the introduction of Mobile Application (McLean & Osei-Frimpong, 2019). MA technologies supported by data analytics are used increasingly by companies as a response to improve revenue/profit margin pressures, to meet increased expectations from customers. Better customer-brand relationships (Evans, 2019) can be achieved and alters the way business interact with their customers.. Mobile Apps (MA) deployment by organizations at different customer touch points strategically can bring significant benefits which are significant to organizations/retailers and a possible increase in customer satisfaction.

An ordinary consumer who is accustomed to traditional shopping is excited to see the emergence of new kind of shopping i.e., Mobile Apps (MA) , where he/she can order / purchase all kinds of goods & avail service at one place without much difficulty. The consumer is excited to see Goods ranging from groceries to cosmetics are packed neatly and been delivered at his residence without extra charge.

Mobile Apps (MA) is a new concept in business world and is receiving great publicity and importance within a shorter period of time, which is result of farsightedness and evolution by retailers. Mobile Apps (MA), is a new type of retailing to serve consumer needs, which has brought a revolutio in retail merchandising.

Being a self-service system, which will have an impact on the economy & has brought innovation in shopping , brought improvements in the Packaging & storage techniques , brought improvements in the techniques of selling, display of products , brought improvements in retail distribution.

Like any other business, Mobile Apps (MA) has a dependency on the confidence and trust by the consumers , as retailers has to provide customers with goods & service with the accepted quality at the right price.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- Prasanta Kr. Chopdar, Nikolaos Korfiatis, V.J. Sivakumar, Miltiades D. Lytras(2018), As part of this study the authors have examined the factors to predict the usage behavior and behavioral intention of consumers towards mobile shopping apps adoption in India and USA
- Marriott, H. R., Williams, M. D., & Dwivedi, Y. K. (2017),study has analyzed mobile distribution channel literature and have not analyzed the literature on mobile shopping system categories
- Monsuwé, T. P., Dellaert, B. G., & De Ruyter, K. (2004),In their study the authors have proposed framework to expand researcher's understanding on the attitude & intention of consumer's shopping online as studies on the factors which drives towards online shopping has been fragmented, even though the consumers who shop frequently online on the Internet.
- Zhou, T. (2016), This research examined user switching from online stores to mobile stores by integrating enablers
- McLean, G., Al-Nabhani, K., & Wilson, A. (2018), this study looks at how customers use mobile m-commerce applications from merchants. In order to construct a Mobile Application consumer Experience Model (MACE), the research attempts to comprehend the aspects that might influence the consumer experience when using merchants' m-commerce mobile applications.
- Liu, L., Zhang, L., Ye, P., & Liu, Q. (2018),This study's primary goals are to build a user satisfaction structure model of mobile learning applications (APPs), or software created to operate on mobile devices, from the viewpoint of the participants in mobile learning, and to examine the variables that affect participants' happiness with APPs

Framework

S. No	Construct	Type of variable
1	Stimuli Influence	Independent variable
2	Adoption Drivers	Independent variable
3	Satisfaction	Dependent variable

Need for the study

The current investigation has been undertaken towards the consumer behaviour study objectively through demographic parameters with special reference to Mobile Apps (MA) which is upcoming and novelty to the consumers. Also an attempt has been made to evaluate the consumer preferences for various products and their motivation towards Mobile Apps (MA). This study tries to bring certain facts which require further investigation.

Research Gap

- Previous studies has investigated adoption on specific contexts such as mobile banking (Chen, 2013), mobile games (Jiang et al., 2015), mobile learning (MacCallum et al., 2014). Few studies or Less research has studied/ investigated or carried out to identify the factors influencing the adoption of mobile apps.
- Previous studies failed to address how students in developing countries are using mobile apps for mobile online shopping (Chau et al., 2021; Faqih & Jaradat, 2015)

Objectives

H0: There is no significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction

H1: There is significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction

H0: There is no significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction

H1: There is significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to explore the Consumers Adoption Behaviour towards Mobile Apps (MA), descriptive research design is employed by the researcher. Data is collected from users of Mobile Apps (MA) through a well- designed questionnaire.

Questionnaire Design

Data is collected from users of Mobile Apps (MA) through a well-designed questionnaire. The questionnaire construction for this study is divided into multiple parts. The first part of the questionnaire collects the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part collect *Stimuli Influence* factors, *Adoption Drivers* and *Satisfaction* and the fourth part measures the scaling technique

Reliability

Pilot study has been carried out to confirm the research questionnaire responses are reliable. Questionnaire used in the pilot study has been verified by involving the users of Mobile Apps (MCA). Required changes in the questionnaire has been done based on the feedback on the users who have participated in the study. The reliability of the variables used in this questionnaire has been tested through Cronbach's alpha, which was above 0.70. This shows that the questionnaire has a high reliability value.

Sampling Technique

In this study, purposive sampling technique has been applied to collect the primary data from users of Mobile Apps (MA). In this way primary data has been collected.

Statistical Tools

PLS-SEM also known as is used to estimate model by probing the relationship between independent variables on dependent variable. The researcher has employed the Partial Least Squares Path Modeling for influence of independent variables with respect to dependent variable. In social science research, PLS-SEM, being a statistical data analysis methodology is used increasingly in social science research to develop or propose an extension to some theory. The following tables represents the statistical analysis of the proposed model. The statistical inference was drawn from the t values and p values and were as mentioned below. The proposed hypothetical relationships between the variables under the study was analysed and interpretations were drawn based on the t and p values

	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O-STDEV))	P Values
Stimuli Influence -> Satisfaction	0.126	0.128	0.061	2.064	0.04
Adoption Drivers -> Satisfaction	0.128	0.128	0.066	1.947	0.05

H0: There is no significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction

H1: There is significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction

Hypothesis was proposed to understand the significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction. To test this hypothesis, the p values and t value statistics were considered. If the p value was found to be less than 0.05, then relationship was considered to be significant. From the above table we can understand that the t value was found to be 2.064 and the p value was found to be 0.04. From this we can understand that the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. This tells that there exists significant influence of stimuli influence on satisfaction. It gives a clear indication that stimuli influence on satisfaction.

H0: There is no significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction

H1: There is significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction

Hypothesis was proposed to understand the significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction. To test this hypothesis, the p values and t value statistics were considered. If the p value was found to be less than 0.05, then relationship was considered to be significant. From the above table we can understand that the t value was found to be 1.947 and the p value was found to be 0.05. From this we can understand that the null hypothesis was rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted at 5% level of significance. This tells that there does not exists significant influence of adoption drivers on satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Technological innovation is indeed important to economic growth and the enhancement of human possibilities. Organization vision and business objectives gain competitive advantage through comprehensive technology strategic initiatives by identifying opportunities for differentiation, disrupting traditional business models and Innovation for being an industry leader through digital transformation and to achieve revenue growth of business.

Digital transformation initiatives shapes organization success in the digital era to enhance business processes, products and services, fostering cross-functional collaboration, compliance with regulations, implement measures to safeguard organization's sensitive information, improved operational efficiency through streamlining processes and leveraging automation. Technology infrastructure has to be ensured for scalability and efficiency by establishing processes for effective technology operations.

Enhanced Customer experience, Improved Customer satisfaction, and Value creation by leveraging technology through identifying digital touchpoints, customer expectations, customer needs and seamless interactions across channels in a rapidly evolving digital landscape.

Mobile Apps (MA), protects consumer interests and it discourages against high prices; i.e., provides goods & services to consumers at low prices when compared to open market, by ensuring correct weight & avoiding malpractices.

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